

Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science services - CORBEL -

Deliverable D6.5

Prototype implementation of distributed automated data access request, review and authorization and delivery systems

WP6 – Data access, management and integration

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes research infrastructures' prototypes for granting a researcher an authorisation to access research data encouraging secondary use of data that is already collected. This deliverable further describes prototypes for delivering the decision on the granted access rights to the environment that enforces access control. The goal of this deliverable is to document and disseminate existing approaches in contributing research infrastructures.

The main use case in this deliverable is that data access requires authorisation because of its sensitive nature, for instance, if it involves samples from humans. Alternatively, it is possible that the data per se is not sensitive and suited to become public but cannot be shared pending the publication of the research results or filing a patent application. These two use cases are complementary and can be covered by the same technical approaches.

Since this deliverable focuses on accessing research data, access to other kinds of assets (such as, instruments, biological samples and computing capacity) is out of scope. Transfer of research data between datacentres (including legal considerations of cross-national transfers) is also not covered in this deliverable.

This deliverable first presents the key concepts, then previous work in life sciences and beyond as well as within relevant standards bodies (in particular, Global Alliance for Genomics and Health). Finally eight prototype implementations are presented from the contributing research infrastructures, including ELIXIR services for registered and controlled access, BBMRI-ERIC's Colorectal cancer cohort and Negotiator, EGA's work on DUO, BBMRI-NL Podium, SOLVE-RD Analysis Sandbox and LifeCycle Federated cohort analysis using DataShield. Before data access authorisation and delivery can be carried out, a researcher needs to be identified and their identity authenticated to a sufficient level of assurance. Existing approaches to researcher authentication are described here to the extent necessary for data access authorisation.

Project objectives

This deliverable has contributed to the following objectives described in Work Package 6 Description of Work:

- a) 1. Identify and map infrastructure extensions required supporting the BMS pilots, cognisant of general infrastructure standards and practices.
- b) 7. Deliver federated authentication and access solution to data service provider selected by the project who support BMS ESFRI data management, analyses, deposition and distribution
- c) 8. Improve interoperability with European e-infrastructures and leverage existing investments these capacities within the biomedical and life science domain.

See Appendix A for details on the contribution.

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background

1. Identity and access management

Identity and Access Management (IAM) is the area of information security which represents entities (in this deliverable: natural persons who are users of information systems) with digital identities and manages their access to organisational assets. This section introduces the IAM basic concepts used in computer science. The readers already familiar with them can move directly to section 2.

1.1. Basic concepts

In computer science, a **(digital) identity** is an abstraction of a user in an information system. An identity consists of attributes describing a user, such as their unique identifiers, name, contacts, roles and permissions in the context of the information system. Management of user's identities, authenticating them and letting them access only the services they are authorised to is called **identity and access management (IAM)**, although in the research and education sector, the term of **authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI)** is also popular.

Authentication is the process which builds a connection between persons in-real-life and their digital identity, represented by the identifier. This connection is created any time a user logs in, and during that session the information system knows that, to the extent of the reliability of the authentication mechanism, the person who has logged in is the legitimate holder of that identity. Classic way of authentication is a password which is still widely used despite its vulnerability to many kinds of fraud (such as, guessing, phishing and sniffing) and its holders' poor practice (selecting a too simple password, writing it down, exposing it to others). More reliable authentication can be achieved by requiring simultaneous presence of several authentication factors, such as accompanying the password with a physical token. This is called multi-factor authentication (MFA).

Although MFA can help with password fraud, it alone does not guarantee the **assurance of identity authentication**. Related standards, such as ISO 29115 [ISO 29115], cover several accompanying factors, most importantly¹ the way the user's identity proofing is carried out. Some services deem it adequate that the user has self-registered an identity (therefore self-asserted who they are), but many services require some level of identity proofing, which in its classic form is done by the user showing up personally at a registration desk (often called a registration authority, RA) where their government-issued photo-id is verified.

Authorisation is the process where the owner of an asset manages who can access and use it. Different authorisation models will be described in section 1.2. Authorisation culminates to an **access control decision** which is carried out and enforced when the user wants to use an asset. It can be expressed using the following function:

¹ ISO29115 covers also other aspects, such as credential revocation/renewal and credential service provider's information security management but they are omitted here for brevity.

$f(S,O,A,e)=\#TRUE$ or $\#FALSE$

Where

S (subject) is the authenticated identity of the user

O (object) is the asset the subject wants to act on (such as a dataset)

A (action) is the action the subject wants to perform on the object (such as, download)

e (environment) describes environmental factors influencing the access control decision (such as time or the network the user is coming from)

The result of the function is a yes/no answer to the question “Is subject S permitted to do action A to object O under the environment conditions e?”

The third “A” in IAM is audit which means the system being able to produce the necessary audit trail and reports to its owner and other persons responsible for the system’s use. On one hand it means log management; who has used the system when, what actions they have done, and who has authorised the actions? On the other hand it means identity management; what existing users the system has and what current permissions they possess?

In the European Economic Area, the General Data Protection Regulation is underpinning the importance of IAM. The data controller has an obligation to implement the necessary technical and organisational measures to protect the integrity and confidentiality of the personal data [GDPR, article 5(1)(f)], which can be partly covered by proper systems to authenticate and authorise users. The audit and reporting functionality can further help the data controller with their obligation to demonstrate [GDPR, Article 5(2)] they comply with the regulation.

1.2. Access control models

The previous section introduced a function that can be used for evaluating user access rights. This section presents some key access control models that the function can adopt for deciding if the parameters S, O, and A result in a positive access control decision.

An access control matrix is a classic access control model and well-known from storage file systems. In the example below (Table 1) subjects (users) are represented by rows, objects (files) by columns and actions by the cell values. User Alice has read access to files Dataset123 and Dataset789. User Bob has read access to Dataset456 and read and write access to Dataset789 -- he is also the owner of that dataset (potentially the researcher who has produced the dataset) and can grant other users (such as, Alice) read access to it.

Object (file) Subject (user)	Dataset123	Dataset456	Dataset789
Alice	read	-	read
Bob	-	read	read, write, owner

Table 1. Example of an access control matrix. A column of an access control matrix is called an access control list.

Downside of an access control matrix is that it does not document why a particular subject has received access rights to an object -- Alice might have had to convince Bob by presenting him her research plan to justify her access rights but we cannot see that in the table. Therefore it scales poorly when the number and turnover of subjects, objects and actions grows.

Role-based access control (RBAC) has been a subject for research in computer science in the 1990's [e.g. FERR92, FERR95, SAND96, BARK97, FERR00] and is nowadays a mainstream access control model. It introduces an additional layer of abstraction between the subject and object called a role. In RBAC, users are assigned roles which describe, for instance, their position and job in their home organisation. This information is typically best managed by the authorised representative of the home organisation. One user can have several roles and several users can have the same role. Roles are then assigned to permissions to act on the objects. That information is typically best managed by the owner of the object which in a federated environment can be outside the users' home organisation.

Figure 1. In role-based access control, users are assigned roles which are further assigned permissions to perform actions on objects.

Figure 1 introduces an example where the roles are research group memberships. Users A and B are members of Research group 1, user B being also the group's Principal Investigator (PI). Users B and C are further members of Research group 2. The Research group 1 has received a permission to access dataset X (potentially by virtue of presenting a data access application to a competent data access committee). The Research Group 1 has also received computing quota from IaaS cloud Y and can launch a virtual machine there. Anyone holding a membership of Research group 1 can use these permissions. The scalable split of responsibility in RBAC allows the involved parties to do what they are best fit to do; research group memberships are managed by the university, dataset access by a competent data access committee and cloud access by the cloud site.

The example above involved actually two kind of roles; User B was a PI and User A a regular member of the research group. To express this, a role hierarchy is integral to RBAC. Figure 2 adds this level of detail to the example presented in Figure 1. User A has a member role in Research group 1, but User B has the PI role which is a child role of member. This implies User B is also a member of Research Group 1 (and therefore has all the permissions a member has) but with the extra role receives some new permissions

the Object owners have granted to PIs only. Only PIs can submit data access applications for (new) datasets and apply for compute quota from the cloud. Once granted, also regular Research group 1 members (including the PI him/herself) can then use the permissions.

Figure 2. Hierarchy of roles in Research Group 1 exposed.

RBAC has been later extended to attribute-based access control (ABAC) [YUAN05] where permissions can be associated not just to roles but to any kind of attributes (or any combination of them) for a user.

1.3. Enforcing access control

Section 1.1 introduced a function to describe access control and section 1.2 some models for the function to produce the access control decision based on its parameters. Once the access control decision is made, it needs to be enforced by the system component responsible for ensuring only authorised users can actually access the service. The access control enforcement can be done by the same system component that makes the access control decision but in a federated environment (as the prototypes in section 4 will show) it is becoming common that these responsibilities are distributed both organisationally and geographically.

Figure 3. A policy enforcement point enforces the access control decision done by a policy decision point, based on the information received from a policy administration point.

RFC 2904 [RFC 2904] and XACML [XACML] define and Figure 3 depicts how the responsibility of access control enforcement can be split in a distributed environment. A Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) intercepts the user's access request to a resource and queries a Policy Decision Point (PDP) if the request should be served. The PDP evaluates the request based on the authorisation policies, in particular those managed by the Policy Administration Point (PAP).

In the context of distributed access to research data,

- a PEP might be a computing environment (IaaS, PaaS or SaaS cloud) where a researcher wants to carry out computing on the data.
- a PDP might be the (potentially centralised) database where researchers' permissions to access data are stored and delivered to the PEP.
- a PAP might be a data access committee and associated IT systems managing access to the datasets.

These three functions can be carried out by different geographically distributed organisations.

1.4. Dynamic separation of duties

Some research infrastructures [e.g. HOLLU16, p65] have indicated their access control model requires dynamic separation of duties. Although a user may have authorisation to act on two (or more) objects in general, to avoid a conflict of interest, the system component enforcing access must ensure the user cannot act on them simultaneously.

Figure 4. In dynamic separation of duties the User B cannot use their permission (see the red cross) to access Dataset Z while currently working actively in Research group 1.

Figure 4 above extends the example presented in section 1.2 and Figure 1. User B is a member of Research group 1 and Research group 2. As a member of Research group 1 User B can read Dataset X and as a member of Research group 2 read Dataset Z. Here the dynamic separation of duties implies that User B must not be able to read both Dataset X and Y at the same time (i.e. in the same session). In

life sciences, unwarranted access and correlation of information between datasets could result in unjustified exposure of patient information, thus thwarting their privacy.

In life sciences, dynamic separation of duties is traditionally carried out contractually in a data access agreement i.e. the researcher has no mandate to correlate the data with those of other projects. In computer science, dynamic separation of duties can be enforced also technically, for instance, by requiring a user to select the role (the research group) they are currently working on and the computing environment exposes them just to the proper datasets.

2. Previous work

The previous section introduced some key concepts and approaches of identity and access management. This section presents related previous work in the research and education sector. Cross-discipline collaboration forums and projects are introduced first, followed by those in the life science sector in Europe and beyond. Finally, some existing IAM services in life sciences are presented as an infrastructure for data access authorisation in the subsequent sections.

2.1. Federated identity management and identity federations

The federated identity management concept emerged in early 2000's to cater access management scenarios where a user wants to use a single identity to access (initially web-based) services in different security domains on the Internet. Nowadays, the most widely used federated identity management protocols are SAML (Security Assertion Mark-Up Language) and OpenID Connect.

Figure 5. In federated identity management, a service (service provider) delegates user authentication to an identity provider server managed by the user's home organisation.

Figure 5 describes a scenario where the users' Home organisation issues a username and password (or other means for authentication) that can be used to access all relying services (sometimes called service providers, SP). When they need to log in to a service, the home organisation's identity provider server authenticates them and releases their attributes (such as a unique identifier and role description) to the relying service.

Federated identity management has many security benefits if the home organisation is the organisation the user is affiliated with (e.g. the university or research institution employing the researcher). The user's home organisation is usually in a position to perform reliable identity proofing for the user and make sure their attributes are fresh and accurate. When the user departs, the home organisation can close their account promptly which is sufficient to close their access to all relying services.

Figure 6. An identity federation (a) connects identity providers (IdP) and service providers (SP). eduGAIN interfederation service (b) further connects identity federations.

There are thousands of research and education institutions globally. To organise the policies and practices under which federated identity management can be done, national research and education networks (REFEDS²) have established identity federations which are associations of organisations that come together to exchange information as appropriate about their users and resources to enable collaborations and transactions [eduGAIN]. This is depicted in Figure 6(a). An identity provider registered to a federation can enable their users to log in to the service providers registered to the federation and service providers accept user logins from the federation's identity providers. GEANT e-infrastructure is further running a service called eduGAIN (Figure 6(b)) which enables interfederation for identity and service providers belonging to different federations.

2.2. Cross-discipline collaboration forums and projects

Federated identity management for research (FIM4R³) is a global cross-discipline network of IAM professionals in research infrastructures and services. After its first meeting at CERN in June 2011, FIM4R has had 12 face-to-face meetings to compare and articulate different disciplines' needs on IAM, in particular on federated identity management.

FIM4R works on voluntary capacity collating participants' IAM requirements and presenting them to stakeholders for action. FIM4R's latest contribution is the Federated Identity Management for Research Collaborations version 2 white paper [FIM4R18] which presents 40 recommendations to the stakeholders, including the identity providers, identity federations and eduGAIN, research communities, research service providers, software developers and standards bodies.

² <http://www.refeds.org/>

³ <https://fim4r.org/>

Partly based on FIM4R's first white paper [FIM4R13] and GEANT e-infrastructure community's work [TERENA12], the European Commission has funded, and the GEANT e-infrastructure, coordinated two projects, **AARC**⁴ (5/2015-4/2017) and **AARC2** (5/2017-4/2019) to address the increased need for federated access and for authentication and authorisation mechanisms by research and e-infrastructures. The AARC project consortiums consisted of research and e-infrastructure organisations and focused on

- research and e-infrastructure AAI architectures (reference models for designing the technical AAI services, including a blueprint architecture for a research and e-infrastructure AAI);
- policies (incident response framework, identity authentication assurance, data protection, acceptable usage);
- pilots within the stakeholder communities;
- training (workshops within the community and beyond) and outreach of the project deliverables and outcomes.

Among the Life Science research infrastructures, BBMRI, ELIXIR, Instruct and INFRAFRONTIER have been represented in AARC or AARC2 project consortiums. In the projects their work has focused on the identity authentication assurance and a pilot on Life Sciences AAI that is further elaborated in the next section.

2.3. Life Science collaboration forums and projects

CORBEL WP5 project ("Enabling common solutions for user access") has been the home for biological and medical sciences research infrastructures' collaboration on IAM in Europe.

In its initial meeting in spring 2016 in Paris the research infrastructures agreed to start collaboration by gathering use cases for a common AAI service and develop a requirements specification based on the use cases. The requirements specification was presented in a GEANT community conference [LIND18] and used as a basis for the a pilot within the AARC2 project (see the previous section). In the pilot, the e-infrastructures (EGI, EUDAT and GEANT) deployed an AARC blueprint architecture compatible AAI service ("Life Science AAI") that was piloted with a small number of test users and services from the BMS research infrastructures. The CORBEL WP5 community served as the stakeholder and customer of the pilot.

In 2018, biological and medical sciences research infrastructures prepared a project plan and grant application for EOSC-Life project that was approved and funded to start in March 2019. EOSC Life project's WP5 focuses on deploying a production Life Science AAI based on the results of the AARC2 pilot, in collaboration with the e-infrastructures.

The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health⁵ (GA4GH) is a policy-framing and technical standards-setting organisation for responsible sharing of human genomic data. Its work is organised into workstreams. The **Data Use & Researcher Identities (DURI)** workstream facilitates and enables the harmonisation of researcher identities by defining who is a bona fide researcher and one or more

⁴ <https://aarc-project.eu/>

⁵ <http://www.ga4gh.org/>

identity providers that respect this definition and can provide a portable electronic identity. DURl will also generate a data use ontology (DUO, section 3.2 below) that will be used to both state data use restrictions as well as researchers' purposes. The **Data security** workstream is developing a protocol profile for delivering the researcher identity claims from the identity provider to the relying service. ELIXIR is participating in the DURl work and is currently holding a workstream co-chair position.

2.4. Research infrastructures' own IAM services

Traditionally, the identity and access management functions are directly integrated to services who have their own user databases and integrated access control functions for authenticated end uses. ELIXIR and BBMRI are the first European BMS research infrastructures who have detached the IAM functionality to make it a dedicated AAI service serving several relying services. Both approaches are aligned with the AARC Blueprint architecture (section 2.2).

ELIXIR AAI [LIND18b] is the ELIXIR compute platform service for authenticating researchers and helping the relying services to decide their permissions. It has been developed using external and ELIXIR's own funding and was launched in November 2016. In the end of 2018 it had 2174 registered users and 50 relying services.

Figure 7. ELIXIR AAI authenticates users via an external authentication provider, adds relevant extra attributes (right hand side of the figure) and hands them to the relying services.

ELIXIR AAI is depicted in Figure 7. ELIXIR AAI relies on the researchers' home organisations (via eduGAIN, see section 2.1) or commercial or community alternatives for user authentication. It also manages extra user attributes which are relevant in the context of ELIXIR services. Examples of attributes are the user's role and status as a researcher in their home organisation, their memberships in groups relevant to ELIXIR and permissions to access sensitive datasets. When a user wants to access a relying service, the ELIXIR Proxy IdP collects their attributes and delivers them to the relying services for access control

enforcement. ELIXIR AAI interfaces with the relying services using standard protocols, in particular SAML 2.0 and OpenID Connect.

BBMRI-ERIC AAI uses the same approach as ELIXIR, but focuses on access to sensitive biobanking materials. BBMRI-ERIC AAI has also a “hostel IdP” for reliable identification and authentication of those users (e.g. researchers and clinical care professionals in hospitals) whose home organisation does not support federated identity management. The level of assurance can be stepped up for the Hostel by validating the users’ registration at one of BBMRI-ERIC National Nodes. Both ELIXIR and BBMRI-ERIC AAI are implemented using open-source software components.

3. Data access authorisation in Life Sciences

Section 1 introduced general identity and access management concepts and approaches in computer science and section 2 previous work in life sciences and beyond. This section examines the existing data access authorisation and access control enforcement models in Life Sciences. The focus is mostly in access to human data as other data are usually not supposed to be sensitive and subject to access control. The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health is the key international standards body in the area. However, in some cases also non-human data may need to be access controlled, at least for an embargo period until the research results are published or patented.

3.1. Tiered access to data

Figure 8 below presents the classic way for authorising access to sensitive human data, called **controlled access**. At first the researcher identifies the datasets of interest (1. Data discovery). Traditionally this is done using public catalogues or other means of discovery, without a need to authenticate and further authorise the researcher (hence the grey arrow in the figure). When researchers have identified the datasets of interest, they proceed to request access to it (2. Data authorisation). Normally this is done by presenting a research plan to a data access committee (DAC) nominated by the organisation responsible for the initial data collection. The DAC reviews the research plan and any supplementing information, and following a positive evaluation, decides to authorise the data access. The researchers can then use their permission to access the dataset (3. Access control enforcement), for instance, to download the dataset to their own environment. However, due to the large size and sensitive nature of the datasets, it is becoming common that instead of download the researcher is granted access to a secure computing environment where the datasets are made available for them.

Figure 8. Controlled access is a classic access model for sensitive data. After discovering the dataset, a researcher presents a data access application to a competent data access committee. After a positive evaluation the researcher can use the data access permission in an environment that enforces the access control.

Controlled access implements the classic access control matrix as described in section 1.2. Often the Principal Investigator (PI) applies for data access not just for themselves but also for all members of their research group, adding an element of RBAC to the access control model (see Figure 1). It is also common that the permission is not granted to the researcher personally but coupled to their continuing affiliation with their home organisation; if a researcher departs, their authorization will expire. Assuming a researcher's fresh affiliation is an attribute provided by the AAI system, this implements also ABAC to the data access authorization. Enforcing the research group and affiliation checks imposes challenges to the access control enforcement phase.

In Figure 8 it was assumed that the data discovery phase can be done on fully public sources and does not require any authorisation for the researcher. However, practice has shown that data discovery requires sometimes access to information that for confidentiality reasons cannot be shared publicly; for instance the researcher wants to discover the datasets which have particular allele frequencies that serve the goals of the research project. The need to first enter the DAC process described above for being able to discover if a dataset is relevant would significantly complicate the data discovery process.

To complement controlled access and public access (where the datasets are fully public), the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health is promoting a third access tier called **registered access** [DYKE18]. In registered access (Figure 9), users who have been demonstrated to be researchers in good standing (a “bona fide researcher”) and have agreed to the terms of registered access (e.g. “I agree to forego any attempt to identify individuals represented in the datasets”) can access data whose sensitivity is limited, without a need to enter the DAC process.

Figure 9. Global Alliance for Genomics and Health promotes 3-tier access model for sensitive data. (Source: www.ga4gh.org)

Registered access is an implementation of role-based access control. In registered access, a researcher who has received bona fide credentials can access any service in the registered access tier without further administrative work. This reduces the DACs' administrative work and the latency observed by the researcher before they can start data access. An example of a registered access service is a Beacon that will be described later in section 4.1.

3.2. GA4GH: DUO for controlled access data

As mentioned in the previous section, a data access committee (DAC) reviews the data access applications to determine if access should be granted to controlled access datasets. A key factor affecting the review process is the purpose for which the patients have donated (“consented”) their samples. For instance, if a patient has donated personal samples for not-for-profit diabetes research, it is an obligation for the DAC to reject any data access application for commercial or non-diabetes use.

The Data Use subgroup of GA4GH has launched a Data Use Ontology (DUO) specification that introduces standard codes describing the permitted use of a dataset. The intention is that datasets are described using DUO codes and the researchers can use the codes to search for datasets compatible with their research projects.

DUO codes can be further utilised in the data authorisation process. As part of their data access applications researchers can use DUO codes to describe their research purpose. Electronic tools can then be used by the DACs to match those DUO codes to those of the datasets the researcher requested access to. Presently, this enables electronic tools to make proposals to the DAC if an application should be accepted or rejected, with the ultimate aim to fully automate the approval process for common use restrictions.

3.3. GA4GH: Research identification and access claims

Whether based on controlled access, registered access or some other model, the user’s authorisation to access a service needs to be delivered from the PDP to the PEP for enforcement, as described in section 1.3. This section describes the GA4GH work for expressing the researchers’ authorisations as their attributes and using standard protocols for delivering them to the PEP.

The Researcher Identity subgroup of GA4GH is developing a specification for expressing researchers’ roles and credentials for registered and controlled access services. The attributes (or claims, as dubbed by the specification) are expressed by claims providers (such as, ELIXIR AAI, see section 2.3) and consumed by relying services, such as computing clouds or beacons. The current draft presents claims for describing

- researcher’s affiliation and role in their home organisation;
- researcher’s qualification as a bona fide researcher;
- the attestations the researcher has made for registered access;
- the controlled access datasets or other objects the researcher is permitted to use.

The researcher identity and access claims are further mounted on standard protocols (OAuth2 and OpenID Connect, or OIDC), as defined by the GA4GH Data security workstream in the GA4GH Authentication/Authorisation specification. The specification introduces an architecture where compatible claims provider (called OIDC brokers) authenticate the user and assemble the claims to standard tokens for being consumed by the Relying Parties (RP) for access control enforcement. An example deployment will be introduced in section 4.1 below.

4. Prototype implementations

This section identifies and studies prototype implementations for data access request, review, authorisation and delivery within the stakeholder community. The prototypes are analysed in particular to identify their role as described in section 1.3 (see Figure 10 below for convenience); if they are Policy Administration Points, Policy Decision Points or Policy Enforcement Points.

Figure 10. The reference diagram for analysing the role of the prototype implementations (see section 1.3 for details).

4.1. ELIXIR service for registered access

ELIXIR has developed a prototype [FIUM19] of a service for registered access (section 3.1) following the definition of GA4GH. The prototype (Figure 11) together with the ELIXIR registered-access Beacon covers the PAP, PDP and PEP functions.

Figure 11. ELIXIR AAI manages access for ELIXIR registered-access Beacons

Bona fide status management (PAP) service is the ELIXIR AAI service component that assigns a bona fide attribute to proper users of ELIXIR AAI, following Dyke et al [DYKE18]:

1. Users need to demonstrate they are a researcher either by
 - a. the user's home organisation confirming they are a researcher, which can be done either programmatically (by virtue of the eduPersonScopedAffiliation attribute released by the home organisation, see section 2.1) or manually (a dedicated person representing the home organisation elevates the user to a researcher status), or
 - b. another bona fide researcher satisfying the condition 1.a above vouches for their status as a bona fide researcher.
2. Users need to make the attestations required for registered access.

Once a person satisfies both conditions 1 and 2 above, ELIXIR AAI assigns them automatically the attribute that describes their permissions for registered access.

ELIXIR Proxy IdP (PDP) is the ELIXIR access management component (see section 2.4) that authenticates the user and releases necessary attributes to the service relying on ELIXIR AAI. For services in the registered access tier, the Proxy IdP releases the user attribute describing them as bona fide researchers for registered access services. The attribute has currently a proprietary format but will be migrated to follow the GA4GH RI claims specification (section 3.3) when available.

Beacon is a genomic data discovery protocol defined by GA4GH. Users can perform searches on databases with samples consented for research use, for instance, “Do you have information about the allele C at position 32,936,732 on chromosome 13?”. From patient privacy perspective it is deemed to be safe to provide a binary yes/no answer even to any (unauthenticated) user, but details on the matching samples (e.g. how many samples match the search criteria) may expose the patients to a privacy threat. However, the human data community has considered that the benefits of registered access outweigh the residual risks.

ELIXIR Beacon (PEP) service contains eight individual Beacons managed by different ELIXIR nodes (Belgium, EMBL-EBI, Finland, France, Sweden, Netherlands, Spain, Switzerland). These Beacons can also be queried through the Beacon Network⁶ provided by GA4GH. ELIXIR Beacon supports searches both in the public and in the registered access tier.

4.2. ELIXIR service for controlled access

ELIXIR has implemented a prototype [LIND18c] for controlled-access data which covers data authorization (PAP) and delivery (PDP) and enforcement (PEP) of data access, as described in Figure 12.

Figure 12. ELIXIR AAI manages access for controlled access data. Access rights are enforced in the CPouta cloud.

REMS (Resource Entitlement Management System, [LIND13]) is an open-source software component implemented by ELIXIR-Finland for managing access rights to resources, in particular to datasets. Researchers can apply for access rights to datasets, and dataset owners (or their representatives, such as DACs) can process and approve, reject or return the applications for amendment. REMS manages also the necessary reporting on effective permissions.

REMS (PAP) has been piloted with the EGA (European Genome-phenome Archive); users log in to REMS with their ELIXIR ID (section 2.3) and apply for access rights to an EGA dataset for themselves and their

⁶ <https://beacon-network.org/>

research group members. After the approval, REMS outputs the permissions to the EGA which has always the authoritative information on dataset permissions.

A researcher can download their permitted datasets from the EGA to their own environment or access them in a computing environment in a datacenter where they have been replicated. For the latter case, ELIXIR has developed a prototype where the user can log in to the environment using **ELIXIR AAI Proxy IdP (PDP)** which fetches the list of the authenticated user's permitted datasets from the EGA using a REST API, assembles them to an access token following the OAuth2 standard, and delivers them to the computing environment. The access token is currently using a proprietary format but will be migrated to the GA4GH RI claims (section 3.3) compliant format when available.

ELIXIR-Finland has developed a prototype for enforcing access in the **CPouta IaaS cloud (PEP)**. After launching and logging in to a virtual machine in CPouta, the user runs a script to mount the datasets to their virtual machine. The script authenticates the user against ELIXIR AAI, retrieves the access token with the dataset permissions and delivers it to the storage server in the computing environment for enforcement. The storage server validates the token and enforces access to authorised files.

4.3. DUO prototype at EGA

This section extends the previous section by describing how the EGA has implemented DUO (section 3.2) to classify the data use conditions on datasets held by the EGA. DUO codes are applied to datasets, which are currently the most granular unit of data access conditions at EGA. When a dataset is created, it must reference a data access policy describing the applicable data use conditions. EGA now supports DUO to determine the data use conditions within a policy, which is defined within the Policy schema⁷. Adding a structured representation of DUO to the Policy schema ensures DUO is consistently applied to different datasets by different DACs.

Once a dataset is released the DUO terms are represented on the EGA website, and are fully searchable⁸, which allows users to query datasets of interest depending on their research use. For example, a user may search the EGA for datasets that may be used in 'For profit research'. The next stage, working in association with ELIXIR AAI and the GA4GH DURl workstream, is to link the DUO to the DAC process, which will allow a researcher to indicate their proposed research purpose in a data application and allow the DAC to electronically match the research purpose to the data use conditions of one or more datasets, potentially streamlining the process of granting access.

EMBL-EBI BioSamples is another service for storing and supplying descriptions and metadata about biological samples used in research and development by academia and industry. BioSamples is open access, holding open-access attributes for a particular sample, while the EGA holds the controlled-access attributes for the same sample. The EGA and BioSamples have worked together to add DUO descriptions also to EGA samples in BioSamples⁹. In that prototype, 177 datasets with over 24000 samples

⁷ <https://github.com/enasequence/schema/blob/master/src/main/resources/uk/ac/ebi/ena/sra/schema/EGA.policy.xsd>

⁸ e.g. <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001004201>

⁹ e.g. <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/samples/SAMEA2483050>

administered by the Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute Data Access Committee are described in BioSamples using DUO codes. This allows researchers to find controlled-access datasets and samples via BioSamples, based upon a combination of high-level phenotype and data use conditions. The search results will link to both the dataset in the EGA and individual samples in BioSamples and the EGA. This has been further leveraged by the GA4GH SearchAPI to enable federated queries over BioSamples/EGA and other remote datasets.

4.4. BBMRI-ERIC Colorectal Cancer Cohort (CRC-Cohort)

Figure 13. CRC Cohorts follow a 3-tier access model (section 3.1).

Within the ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC project, there is a Europe-wide collection of more than 10,000 colorectal cancer cases. The collection has been successfully completed in March 2019. As per CRC-Cohort Data Protection Policy [HOLU17], the CRC-Cohort will be made accessible in 3 different modes, following the 3-tier access model proposed by GA4GH (see section 3.1):

- (Mode-1) Public (non-authenticated) search and browsing access to highly aggregated metadata describing the CRC-Cohort published in the BBMRI-ERIC Directory¹⁰ to ensure the basic findability of the cohort.
- (Mode-2) Secure authenticated search access by querying the anonymized data set with relatively low residual risk of re-identification via search functionality using the upcoming BBMRI-ERIC Locator (see below).
- (Mode-3) Secure authenticated access to the pseudonymized data (= personal data) controlled by a lightweight Access Committee established with members from BBMRI-ERIC and the biobank which provided the data considered for release. Request for the data release will be done using BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator (see the next section).

Implementation of those access models is scheduled for completion before Summer 2019.

For authenticated access for Mode-2, relatively weak authentication will be sufficient, as the data is outside of the personal data domain. The main purpose of Mode-2 is to ensure a user agrees to the terms and conditions, in particular that the user agrees not to re-identify any persons contributing their data. This is enforced (PEP) by the BBMRI-ERIC Locator service¹¹, which allows federating querying of distributed data resources (e.g., biobanks) to obtain anonymized statistics on available datasets, patient cases or biological samples. The search is based on searching through the individual (personal) data that

¹⁰ <https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/>

¹¹ <https://search.germanbiobanknode.de/>

stays at the data source. While the search results are anonymised, the service acknowledges that no anonymisation is perfect while retaining utility of the data. Therefore the residual risk is minimised by requiring all its users to accept the terms and conditions.

Authentication in Mode-3 will require strong assurance, because it will deal with protecting the pseudonymized (= personal) data. The initial authorization of access is subject to an access procedure, involving basically a lightweight variant of committee-controlled access (contributing biobanks have a veto right before release of the data to a particular requester for a particular purpose). Accesses require high assurance for both identity vetting and authentication instances, as described in [AARC19].

4.5. BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator

BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator¹² is a tool that implements policy and procedures to access data and/or biological material from BBMRI-ERIC partner biobanks. It is an implementation of the Policy Access Point functionality (Figure 14).

Figure 14. BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator is a Policy Administration Point for biological samples.

BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator has currently 94 biobankers registered to represent 379 biobank collections, and overall there are close to 200 registered users. The service covers all 20 member countries of BBMRI-ERIC RI and IARC, a subsidiary of the WHO international organization. Hence the service is a core and high-value element of BBMRI-ERIC services, despite the lower numbers of users compared to services dealing with freely available data.

This service is about negotiating access to health-related human data (particularly sensitive data following GDPR) and biological samples in a trustworthy manner. The Negotiator is used by the biobank representatives to negotiate and eventually decide on whether the access to the particular data and sample sets can be granted.

User authentication is a critical part of the functionality, as the biobanks need to be able to trust the authenticity of the users and their requests. BBMRI-ERIC has its own Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (see section 2.4) that manages the user identities and authentication. Before being able to use Negotiator, all users are required to agree to Terms and Conditions for using BBMRI-ERIC Services. When filing applications it is also important to know the user's affiliation, as the organization is typically legally responsible for the research project.

¹² <https://negotiator.bbmri-eric.eu/>

Currently, Negotiator focuses mainly on requesting and authorising access to physical samples. The actual delivery of the samples (access control enforcement) is implemented then directly between the requester and the biobank, not via the Negotiator.

4.6. BBMRI-NL Podium

The BBMRI-NL Request Portal Podium¹³ is an online one-stop-shop to request samples, images and data from multiple Dutch national health registries, health databases, image archives and biobanks. Podium was set up to facilitate access for researchers to bio-materials, clinical images and health data, and to allow linkage of data on subject-level across different biobanks and registries. The linkage is carried out by back-end processes with trusted third parties.

Figure 15. BBMRI-NL Podium is a Policy Administration Point which Data access committees in biobanks and registries to review Researchers' data access applications.

With the Podium portal researchers have a single online entry point to request what they need for their research. Researchers in search of samples, data and/or images can search the BBMRI-NL Catalogue and send their query via Podium to the biobanks and registries. The requests are reviewed and validated by the data access committees of the underlying resources. The requestor is kept updated on the status of the request through Podium.

Delivering the datasets to the researcher (PEP) runs through the existing infrastructure of the underlying services, usually involving several manual parallel steps in different services. Podium has no specific role in that part of the process (at this time). Users in Podium have to be registered though in order to validate their status as bona fide requestors. At this time this is done through a local user database; the next step will be connection to the institutional account of those users through e.g OpenConext¹⁴.

Podium and the BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator (see the previous paragraph) have some overlapping and some complementary functionalities. BBMRI-ERIC and BBMRI-NL are currently investigating whether it would be viable to integrate the two tools for generic use in the BBMRI network.

¹³ <https://podium.bbMRI.nl/>

¹⁴ <https://openconext.org/>

4.7. Solve-RD Analysis Sandbox

Figure 16. Solve-RD Analysis Sandbox is a policy enforcement point relying on data access authorisation done by a competent DAC.

The Solve-RD Analysis Sandbox prototype facilitates collaborative use of sensitive data in the context of rare disease. It takes the form of a virtual HPC cluster, which acts as a virtual research environment where data can be downloaded into (from EGA or directly from partners, using their regular data access authorisation processes) and accessed/processed while adhering to data access committee agreements. Such a virtual research environment is called an online collaborative analytical ‘sandbox’. The prototype has been developed with some support from CORBEL and EXCELERATE projects (via UMCG).

From a bioinformatics researcher perspective the sandbox behaves like a Linux HPC computer cluster. A researcher will login using a standard SSH and then get a Linux shell to operate that sandbox. The sandbox is configured with industry standard workload manager SLURM¹⁵ for execution of large scale analysis on high performance computers. Slurm manages ‘jobs’ (which are the analysis steps and their workflow relationships), i.e., in what order jobs should be executed. Most importantly, Slurm then automatically distributes the work over the compute nodes and takes care of bookkeeping the analyses, ensuring they proceed to completion and that parallel analyses can run without overloading the system.

In addition, the sandbox utilises community best practices for reproducible deployment of such pipelines, including all software and reference data needed (such as EasyBuild¹⁶ and Ansible¹⁷), and that these data can be used in a versioned way to ensure reproducibility (Lmod¹⁸ module system). Finally, the best practice solutions from UMCG¹⁹ have been implemented which use MOLGENIS/compute to configure pipelines of analysis steps and Slurm to execute these analyses.

Using these services the provisioning of an analytical sandbox can be fully automated. This is a complete Linux ‘virtual research environment’, including HPC compute servers, shared storage, analysis pipelines, relevant software and reference data. Each group/consortium can get a “private” analytical sandbox if so desired, ensuring that data is kept private. Moreover, the location of these environments is flexible,

¹⁵ <https://slurm.schedmd.com/>

¹⁶ <https://easybuild.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

¹⁷ <https://www.ansible.com/>

¹⁸ <https://lmod.readthedocs.io/en/latest/#>

¹⁹ <https://wiki.gcc.rug.nl/>

for example in Groningen or at the EMBASSY cloud at EBI which enables secure access to the raw Solve-RD patient data. This service has the potential to become the basis of a diagnostics analysis service ‘in a box’, as cloud facilities are becoming rapidly cheaper and more accessible.

There are plans to integrate the Sandbox to ELIXIR AAI (section 2.4) for user authentication and group management, enabling group managers (such as PIs) to control what tools and data the group members share with whom in the Sandbox. Thereby they can properly comply with the ethical and legal requirements about joint work on sensitive test datasets and new methods. ELIXIR AAI also allows users to sign in using their institution account, and provides compatibility with other services such as EGA.

In the future, it is also possible to extend the Sandbox to consume the Researcher ID claims (see section 3.3) to enforce direct access to the datasets based on the claims provided by the data archive (such as, EGA). A similar setup was described in section 4.2 for an IaaS cloud.

4.8. LifeCycle: Federated cohort analysis using DataSHIELD

Figure 17. DataSHIELD is a policy enforcement point that permits particular operations on particular data items.

Outside of the CORBEL funding UMCG has been working on enabling privacy-protecting access by not sharing any data centrally. Background is that while it is theoretically possible to bring together many individual studies into a single pooled participant-level data analysis, it remains administratively complex because it requires institutional-level collaboration. Moreover, existing material transfer agreements don't scale to many researchers/groups across many institutions and several countries. It is also very challenging to standardise harvesting, data access, data transfers, and archiving of complex datasets with the required level of data security and privacy. To overcome these barriers, instead, analysis scripts are sent around to each data source individually, and only non-sensitive aggregated statistics are shared centrally for integration.

We therefore implemented DataSHIELD²⁰. In situations where data cannot be shared physically. DataSHIELD enables federated analysis using the open source software R to perform data analyses without sharing data. The aim is to enable direct investigation of between-population variation and thus requires an approach dependent upon meta-analysing individual participant data (IPD) across studies rather than simply meta-analysing results across different populations. Analysis requests are sent from a central analysis machine to several data-holding machine storing the harmonised data to be co-analysed. The data sets are analysed simultaneously but in parallel, linked by non-disclosive summary statistics. Analysis is taken to the data – not the data to the analysis.

²⁰ <http://www.datashield.ac.uk/>

Figure 18: Conceptual overview of DataSHIELD. Source: <http://www.datashield.ac.uk/>

The DataSHIELD protocol is implemented in practice within LifeCycle²¹ with some input from CORBEL, in particular in advice and in contributing to their data harmonisation database (outside scope of this deliverable). The result is a series of server configurations and an operational setup of 10+ cohorts now being used for federated analysis. However, we also learned that there are still many limitations, for example, in the context of omics datasets that simply are too large. For those cases we aim to develop alternative federated analysis solutions which might be developed in CINECA or EOSC-Life projects. Therefore LifeCycle joined forces with similar projects (RECAP, InterConnect, amongst others) to submit another EU grant successfully into an infrastructure-oriented project called EUCAN-Connect to further professionalise this approach.

Also for DataSHIELD we strive to integrate the ELIXIR AAI (section 2.4) for user authentication and group management, enabling group managers to control what tools and data they share with whom. There is also potential to consume the researcher ID claims (see section 3.3) to enforce dataset access in DataSHIELD (c.f. section 4.2).

4.9. Summary and analysis

This section presents a summary of the prototypes described above and collates quantitative information on them in Table 2. An analysis on the prototypes is also provided.

Table 2. Quantitative information on users and data providers participating in the prototypes and their role as a Policy administration point (PAP), Policy decision point (PDP) and Policy enforcement point (PEP).

²¹ <https://github.com/lifecycle-project/analysis-protocols/wiki>

Prototype	Number of data providers	Roles
ELIXIR service for registered access	8	PAP, PDP, PEP
ELIXIR service for controlled access	706	PAP, PDP, PEP
DUO prototype at EGA	35	
BBMRI-ERIC Colorectal Cancer Cohort (CRC)	25	PAP, PDP, PEP
BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator	94	PAP
BBMRI-NL Podium	10	PAP
Solve-RD Analysis Sandbox	3	PEP
LifeCycle Federated cohort analysis using DataSHIELD	22	PEP

The assumed approach (section 1.3) to identify the prototypes' role as a Policy administration point (PAP), Policy decision point (PDP) or Policy enforcement point (PEP) highlights the different scopes of the prototypes.

- BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator and BBMRI-NL Podium are PAPs; tools that are used by researchers to contact the data providers and apply for/negotiate data access with them. As a result, the researchers become authorised to access data but the actual data delivery is done elsewhere.
- Solve-RD Analysis Sandbox and LifeCycle Federated cohort analysis using DataSHIELD are PEPs, they are used for analysis on the data and assume the researcher has used some out-of-band mechanism to make the datasets available and accessible for analysis.
- ELIXIR services for registered and controlled access and BBMRI-ERIC CRC provide the "full suite"; they have tools for the researcher to apply for the qualifications for data access (PAP), systems to evaluate the request when a user wants to use their access rights (PDP), and services enforcing the access control decision (PEP).

The components can be geographically and organisationally distributed; the data's original collector or a DAC representing them can use local tools (PAP) to manage data access rights which are archived centrally at a data archive (PDP). For federated computing, the data itself can be replicated to several data centres where data access is enforced (PEP). This approach also supports the scenario where for legal reasons the data itself needs to be retained in a datacentre in a particular country or jurisdiction.

The components described can use emerging standards for communication. In particular, the communication between the components in the PDP and PEP roles can use the existing standards for authentication and authorisation and researcher identity claims (see section 3.3) which supports a federated data analysis scenario.

In the future, the actors should recognise their role in this model and focus on it. The analysis tools and pipelines should not manage access to data themselves but assume a role of a PEP, consuming claims

provided by PDPs to enforce access rights or relying on the computing infrastructure (e.g. a storage system) to do it for them. The data archives and research infrastructures could then focus on developing and deploying tools for managing data access (PAP) and making the access control decisions (PDP) when requested by a PEP.

5. Related and potential future use cases

The work in this deliverable reports current prototypes, in parallel we have identified additional use cases which are emerging. These represent new communities and future use cases and these are therefore documented below. These communities are both consumers of lessons learned from this deliverable and future consumers of the solutions described here.

5.1. Euro-BioImaging Web Portal (EWP)

The Euro-BioImaging Web Portal will be the central access point to all services of the upcoming Euro-BioImaging ERIC, which offers open access in biological and medical imaging to technologies, training and data. The EWP will for instance handle technology access proposals from users including their review and feedback processes, and later also similar processes for training course management and registrations. The EWP will also provide access to Euro-BioImaging data services, currently consisting of a public Image Data Resource (see next section) and an Image Tool Resource, with more being developed in the future. The EWP will include e.g. communication tools, tools for gathering statistics on Euro-BioImaging ERIC operations, quality management tools and tools for incorporating new imaging technologies into the infrastructure. The EWP will also be the “website” of Euro-BioImaging ERIC.

Some services of the EWP are publicly available, while some require login. Access will be granted to everyone who requests it. The administrator can grant additional access rights on a case-by-case basis to non-public EWP tools, such as access proposal moderation, external scientific review, or Euro-BioImaging Node functionality. EWP uses currently ELIXIR AAI (see section 2.4) for login and will be integrated to Life Science AAI (section 2.3), when available.

In addition to the EWP and other centralized services, Euro-BioImaging Nodes, which are “independent” service centers, may offer image data services and data access. The number of these services are likely to increase in the future, and may also be integrated to the centralised Euro-BioImaging services where feasible.

5.2. Image Data Resource (IDR)

Much of the published research in the life sciences includes multidimensional, quantitative image data. These images are routinely used for quantitative measures of biological processes and structures that form the foundation of many of the results published in peer-reviewed life sciences journals. In almost all cases, however, images are presented in published articles in processed, compressed formats that do not accurately convey the quality and complexity of the original image data. The original image data are housed in thousands of individual labs in hundreds of different file formats. The data are difficult for researchers to share and impossible to routinely publish. The recent development of high resolution super-resolved and 3-D imaging techniques using high frame rate cameras has greatly increased this

challenge. Today the sheer size and heterogeneity of image data sets— multi-dimensional image stacks combined with experimental metadata and analytic results— makes image data handling and publication extremely complex, and in practice, rarely achieved. Multi-dimensional images and associated metadata are reduced to single JPEGs in a conventional journal figure, with metadata published, at best, in supplemental data spreadsheets, the antithesis of findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR).

The Image Data Repository (IDR) has been built to demonstrate the capability and utility of publishing complete scientific image data. IDR is populated with community-submitted image datasets, experimental and analytical metadata, and phenotypic annotations (doi: 10.1038/nmeth.4326). The first version of this resource is built and deployed in on EMBL-EBI's Embassy cloud resource²². IDR currently holds ~104 TB of data in ~4.8M multi-dimensional (multi-D) images, and includes all associated experimental (e.g., genes, RNAi, chemistry, geographic location), analytic (e.g., submitter-calculated regions and features), and functional annotations.

In 2018, IDR was accessed by >37,000 IP addresses worldwide, and >100,000 hits/day. It is a maturing service that is now included in FAIRSharing.org and recommended by several journals to their authors (Springer Nature, PLOS One, eLife, among others). IDR will become part of the public bioimage data ecosystem that will be operated by Euro-BioImaging once the EuBi ERIC formally becomes a legal entity in 2019.

To make IDR's TB-scale datasets available for re-analysis, IDR has been connected to a Jupyter notebook-based computational resource²³ that exposes IDR datasets via an API. Authentication is through GitHub OAuth or through ORCID, Google, or LinkedIn. As users have read-only access to public IDR datasets, authentication is used to limit access to authentic users and to filter out bots, spurious usage, etc. No further selection of users of access granting mechanism is used or required.

5.3. Computing capacity

Access to research data is useless without having also access to sufficient capacity for processing the data. Different approaches to accessing computing capacity has been developed for decades, including computing grids in the past decade and cloud computing and containers in this decade. Nowadays computing capacity is available also commercially.

While the size of the datasets has grown, a paradigm change has been suggested. Instead of moving the datasets from a data archive to the researcher's preferred computing center, the researcher who has been granted access to a dataset could access them in a computing environment where they are already available. This approach may also help with legal questions in jurisdictions where local laws or datasets' consent conditions or terms of use prevent moving them abroad (c.f. Section 4.8).

Providing a researcher with access to sensitive data in a secure computing environment can also improve information security. There would be no need for the researcher to download the datasets to their own environment where they may be subject to poor information security practices. Instead, the

²² <http://idr.openmicroscopy.org/>

²³ <https://idr-analysis.openmicroscopy.org/>

users would not be able to download the data but just the results of the computation, enabling them to publish their research results. Such computing environments can be consumers of the data access authorisation and delivery systems described in section 4.

There are different approaches available for computing capacity. Commercial providers are providing cloud capacity. National publicly funded research organisations provide capacity for researchers in their country, and e-infrastructures including EOSC to research communities in general. In the life sciences, there are existing projects and activities, such as the GA4GH cloud workstream and EOSC-Life project's Work Package 7.

6. Conclusions

This deliverable provides an overview of the contributing research infrastructures' data access request, review and authorisation service prototypes and the delivery of the authorisation decision for enforcement. The main focus was on managing access to sensitive human data. The overview was complemented by an introduction to identity and access management in general and in the life sciences sector in particular.

The analysis of the prototypes highlighted three functions:

- **Policy Administration Point (PAP)** is the system component that those responsible for managing authorisations use to grant access. In the classical approach (controlled access) this is a data access committee using an appropriate tool to review a data access application a researcher has submitted, but a new approach with reduced administrative burden called registered access is gaining popularity for data with limited sensitivity. In registered access, a researcher demonstrates they are a researcher in good standing and are granted access to all services belonging to the registered access tier.
- **Policy Decision Point (PDP)** is the system component that is invoked when a researcher wants to use the data access rights they have. The PDP consumes the information administered by the PAP to evaluate if the researcher's request should be accepted or rejected and delivers its decision to the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) for enforcement.
- **Policy Enforcement Point (PEP)** is the system component enforcing the access control decision made by the PDP. In the classic approach, it is a data archive's download site, but an alternative approach where the datasets are made available for the researcher in a secure computing environment is also becoming popular. In that case, the PEP would be the computing environment storage system that enforces the data access authorisation.

It is important to realise that in a distributed environment also these three functions become distributed, both organisationally and geographically. If the datasets are geographically distributed to several data centres, also the PEP resides in the storage systems or applications in the data centers. The PDP should be kept in the organisation where the data is managed, enabling making a consistent access control decision centrally, despite the distributed dataset replicas and PEPs.

In the future, the actors should recognise their role in this model and focus on it; PEPs (such as, analysis pipelines) should not manage data access themselves but use standard protocols (such as, GA4GH claims) to consult the PDP on data access authorisation. For instance, the computing environment could mount the datasets to the filesystem of the virtual machine where the analysis pipeline is running, completely separating the data access authorisation from the application.

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Abbreviations

AAI	Authentication and authorisation infrastructure
ABAC	Attribute-based access control
API	Application programming interface
BMS	Biological and medical sciences
DAC	Data access committee
DNS	Domain name system
DUO	Data use ontology
DURI	Data use and research identification
EGA	European genome-phenome archive
ESFRI	European strategy forum for research infrastructures
EWP	Euro-Biolmaging Web Portal

FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable
IaaS	Infrastructure as a service
IAM	Identity and access management
ID	Identity
IdP	Identity provider
IDR	Image Data Resource
IPD	Individual participant data
IT	Information technology
GA4GH	Global alliance for genomics and health
GDPR	General data protection regulation
MFA	Multi-factor authentication
OIDC	OpenID Connect
PaaS	Platform as a service
PAP	Policy administration point
PDP	Policy decision point
PEP	Policy enforcement point
PI	Principal investigator
RBAC	Role-based access control
RI	Researcher identity
RFC	Request for comments
SaaS	Software as a service
SAML	Security assertion markup language
SP	Service provider
UMCG	University medical center Groningen
XACML	Extensible access control markup language

Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: No

Adjustments made

None

Appendix A: Analysis on contribution to the project objectives

This appendix describes how this deliverable has contributed to the following objectives described in Work Package 6 Description of Work:

Objective 1. Identify and map infrastructure extensions required supporting the BMS pilots, cognisant of general infrastructure standards and practices.

- The ELIXIR prototypes for registered (section 4.1) and controlled (section 4.2) access and BBMRI-ERIC prototype on Colorectal Cancer Cohort (section 4.4) assume an approach of different system components of PAP, PDP and PEP. That approach is further encouraged as a conclusion (section 6).
- The prototypes above respect the 3-tier approach to data access promoted by the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) and can be implemented using GA4GH products, such as the emerging Researcher identity and access claims and Authentication/authorisation profile.
- The ELIXIR prototype for registered access and BBMRI-ERIC prototype for Colorectal Cancer Cohort implement Role-based access control which is a mainstream approach in computer security.

Objective 7. Deliver federated authentication and access solution to data service provider selected by the project who support BMS ESFRI data management, analyses, deposition and distribution

- Section 2.4. introduces the ELIXIR and BBMRI-ERIC prototypes for federated authentication solutions.
- Section 4. introduces eight prototypes for federated access solutions.

Objective 8. Improve interoperability with European e-infrastructures and leverage existing investments these capacities within the biomedical and life science domain.

- Section 2.1 introduces e-infrastructure services and section 2.2. collaboration forums and projects for federated authentication.
- The ELIXIR and BBMRI-ERIC AAI services (section 2.4) implement the AARC Blueprint architecture (section 2.2).